

LEGAL PROTECTION AGAINST LAND ENCROACHMENT OF PUBLIC FACILITIES IN INDONESIA THAT IS EQUITABLE

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to study; (1) Settlement of land grabbing problems in criminal law, (2) Settlement of land encroachment problems in civil law, and (3) Legal protection against land grabbing of public facilities in Indonesia that is fair. The research method used is doctrinal research with normative juridical approach and a case study approach. The results of the study show that; (1) The resolution of the issue of land grabbing is in criminal law as follows: (a) a report or complaint, (b) Transfer of the case to the public prosecutor; (c) Pre-Prosecution, (d) Indictment, (e) litigation; (2) Settlement of Land Custody Cases through civil procedural law as follows: (a) filing of a lawsuit, (b) stage of summons, (c) Preparation for trial; (d) Reading of the Suit, (e) Defendant's Answer. (3) Legal protection against land encroachment of public facilities in Indonesia that is equitable with the concept of a Special Land Court in the Indonesian Judicial System. The special court of land is referred to in the general judicial environment. This court has the authority to examine, handle, adjudicate, and decide all disputes relating to land, both civil and criminal. This court has its own procedural law with material proof to defend the material law Undang Undang Pokok Agraria and other land regulations. This court also has its own specificities, namely in addition to judges, clerks, bailiffs, and secretaries, there are also commissioners, appraisers, and officers Badan Pertanahan Nasional who will at any time provide land data to judges.

Keywords: Legal Protection, Land, Public Facilities, Indonesia, Judicial, Enforcement.

A. PREDECESSORN

One of the identities of a legal state is to provide guarantees and legal protection of the rights of its citizens. As is known, the purpose of law is order, justice and legal certainty, including legal protection for land rights holders. In human life, the existence of the land will not be separated from all human deeds themselves, because the land is a place for man to live and continue his life (Rustiadi, 2012).

The land is a gift from God Almighty to mankind on earth. Therefore, land becomes a basic human need, from birth to death. That man needs land for residence and source of life. Cosmologically, land is where people live, where they work and live, where they come from, and where they go (Lubis & Lubis, 2010)

Recognizing the importance and importance of land, the founders of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia (NKRI) formulated land and natural resources in a concise but very philosophical substantial manner in the constitution, article 33 paragraph (3) of the 1945 Constitution, as follows: "The earth and water and the natural wealth contained therein are controlled by the state and used for the greatest prosperity of the people". Therefore, the use of land must lead to the welfare of the people (Santoso, 2011).

Awareness of the special position of land in the mind of the Indonesian nation is also stated in the Basic Agrarian Law (UUPA) Number 5 of 1960, where in the Basic Agrarian Law it is stated that there is an eternal relationship between the Indonesian nation and land.

Land grabbing is one type of criminal act that occurs in people's lives. Raids carried out by a person or group of people on land owned by others often occur in various regions in Indonesia. In general, the term land grabbing can be interpreted as the act of controlling, occupying, or expropriating land owned by others unlawfully, against rights, or violating applicable legal regulations (Sutedi, 2014).

With regard to this problem, it is necessary to know the protection efforts for holders of rights to property rights in a criminal and civil point of view, in order to uphold justice to achieve welfare for the community, especially the aggrieved parties. This is done in order to find solutions for other parties who also experience the same problem, namely breach or control by parties who do not obtain rights (Alting, 2011).

The purpose of this study is to study; 1) Solving the problem of land grabbing in criminal law, 2) Solving the problem of land grabbing in civil law, and 3) Legal protection against land grabbing of public facilities in Indonesia that is equitable

B. LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Legal Certainty of Land Registration

Legal certainty is the purpose of land registration as a form of legal ownership as stated in Article 19 of UUPA paragraph 1, namely that: "To ensure legal certainty by the government, land registration is held throughout the territory of the Republic of Indonesia according to the provisions regulated by Government Regulations". Given the importance of legal certainty in every land transfer as a result of the sale and purchase of land rights, the UUPA is required to register for the transfer of rights because of the sale and purchase. If studied in more depth, the sale and purchase agreement under the hand remains vulnerable, because it does not provide legal certainty (FX., 2010).

Land ownership has provided benefits and uses in various aspects of life to the owner, both in economic aspects, social aspects, including in relation to development. According to the economic aspect, land can be used for housing, agriculture, plantations, offices, as a place of business, can be used as collateral (dependent rights), rented / contracted and so on. With the holding of land registration, it can be easily known the status or position of a certain piece of land that it wants to know regarding its location, boundaries and area as well as the holder of rights and burdens attached to the land (Parlindungan, 1990).

In terminology land registration comes from the word *cadastre*, a technical term for a record or record, denoting the area, value, and ownership of a piece of land. The word is derived from the Latin *capistratum* which means a register or capita or unit made for Roman land tax. *Cadastre* means the *record* on lands, or the value of the land and its rights holders and for taxation purposes (Effendie, 1993). A *cadastre* can be interpreted as an appropriate tool for providing such a description and identification and as a continuous recording of land rights. Meanwhile, according to Boedi Harsono, land registration is a series of activities carried out by the State / Government continuously and regularly, in the form of collecting certain information or data about certain lands in certain areas, processing, storing, and presenting them for the benefit of the people, in order to provide guarantees of legal certainty in the land sector, including the issuance of evidence and its maintenance (Hairan, 2012). Land registration is distinguished by 3 (three) types, namely tax registration (fiscal *cadastre*) and registration with a certain information system (land information) and registration of land rights (*legal cadastre*). The land registration provisions are a follow-up to Article 19 of Law 5/1960, further provisions are regulated in PP 10/1961 which has been repealed and replaced by PP 24/1997.

Law 5/1960 Article 19 (1) "To ensure legal certainty by the Government, land registration is held throughout the territory of the Republic of Indonesia according to the provisions regulated by a Government Regulation." (2) "The registration mentioned in subsection (1) of this section includes: measurement of land plotting and bookkeeping; b. registration of land rights and transfer of such rights; c. the granting of letters of proof of right, which act as a powerful evidentiary tool." (3) "Land registration shall be held in view of the circumstances of the State and society, the necessity of socioeconomic traffic and the possibility of its implementation, in the consideration of the Minister of Agrarian Affairs." (4) "In a Government Regulation, the costs relating to registration referred to in subsection (1) above are regulated, provided that the incapacitated persons are exempt from payment of such fees."

The scope of land registration activities, includes the following stages: (Bahruddin, 2014)

- 1) Measurement of land mapping and bookkeeping, which produces registration maps and measuring letters, so that certainty is obtained regarding the location, boundaries and area of the land plot in question, otherwise known as the *specialiteit* principle
- 2) Registration of land rights including the right of guarantee of land and the transfer of such rights and other burdens that accompany and attach to the parcel of land in question, as well as a description of who is the subject of the right holder to the parcel of land in question, otherwise known as the *openbaarheid* principle;
- 3) The provision of letters of proof of rights in the form of certificates, which acts as a strong evidentiary tool. The land registration system used in and based on Law 5/1960 is a negative system with a positive tendency or a negative publication system that contains positive elements.

PP 24/1997 Article number 1 "Land registration is a series of activities carried out by the Government continuously, continuously and regularly, including the collection, processing, bookkeeping, and presentation and maintenance of physical data and juridical data, in the form of maps and lists, regarding land plots and units of flats, including the provision of proof of rights for existing land plots and property rights to units of flats and rights certain that weighed on him." (Sutedi, 2010)

2. The Root Cause of Disputes or Land Grabbing of Public Facilities

The conflict that occurs over land is clearly encouraged because of interest. These interests in the occurrence of conflicts so that one or both or more parties commit criminal acts in the field of land. Criminal charges have been committed, such as possessing, harrying and or occupying. However, the problem is that neither the Criminal Code nor the Agrarian laws and regulations have been able to accommodate all of them to ensnare the perpetrators of this land dispute. Moreover, it is related to the recognition and protection of the existence of customary land. Including land issues that occur individually (individually) related to private rights and public rights or civilly (Siregar, 2007).

In general, cases of land grabbing occur because of the landowner's indifference to the assets he owns. In some cases it happens because the landowner gives confidence to others to manage their land which is then made a new land deed without the knowledge of the landowner with bad intentions (Sutedi, 2009). The factor of land grabbing is also due to the ignorance of the victim regarding the ownership of his land has been sold or given to others by the victim's parents. A person or victim of a landowner finds out his land is controlled by another person after being notified by his family and noticing the title papers he has that the land has never been sold/transferred (Murni, 2018).

Land disputes arising from the cultivation of land by the people generally occur over lands of former western rights / eigendom in the form of vacant land. Sometimes, the cultivators worked with local officials to provide information about the whereabouts of the cultivators on the land. The certificate was issued by the Lurah and Camat which was continued to take care of the UN payment of the land. Armed with a certificate from the Lurah and Sub-district, UN payments and ID cards of residents on the land, SKPT and certificates are immediately submitted at BPN (Suripin, 2002).

The techniques of state land tenure in these ways are widely carried out by land brokers, so that if one day the government gives the land rights to investors, then the cultivators with the capital of the brokers begin to make demands to investors as if the land is already his own with the data taken care of above. Most of the country's lands on the riverbanks or around the railroad tracks were often seized by the inhabitants, and in order to maintain the land they often made false certificates.

Unfortunately, the forced and illegal land grabbing was aggravated by the issuance of a certificate of control of land rights by BPN without examining the history / origin of the land in question. Forgery of signatures is also carried out so that a piece of land can be transferred to a third party (Indiraharti, 2009).

According to Maria S.W. Sumardjon, the map of land problems can be grouped into: 1) The problem of people's cultivation of forestry land, plantations, abandoned housing projects, and so on. 2) Problems relating to violations of land reform provisions. 3) Excesses in the provision of land for development purposes. 4) Civil disputes relating to land issues and 5) Issues relating to customary rights of indigenous peoples (Gaol, 2020).

According to Aditjondro, agrarian disputes in Indonesia are multi-dimensional in nature that are not understood only as agrarian disputes, but the tip of the iceberg of various other fundamental types of conflicts, such as conflicts between economic systems, conflicts of majority, conflicts between modern societies versus indigenous peoples, conflicts between states and citizens, conflicts between ecological systems (ecosystems versus industrialism), conflicts between knowledge systems (positivistic knowledge systems) versus the original knowledge system), conflicts between cultures (modern culture versus indigenous culture) as well as conflicts in gender relations (Syarief, 2014).

Land disputes at this time are not simple, for example, it is limited to the people with the people fighting for a piece of land. What happens more is that farmers or people as landowners or cultivators or as units of indigenous peoples fight with other parties who will use the land for business development or capital accumulation. The latter goal was facilitated by the state. Feeling aggrieved, the people also perceived the state as their opponent because the state became a tool of businessmen. Indeed, the government, including law enforcement officials, sided with investors at the expense of the people (Soerodjo, 2002).

Land disputes between the people and the state basically occur as a result of this obsession of power authority to increase economic growth. The reality on the ground is:

- 1) The occurrence of agrarian disputes due to the exploitation of agrarian resources such as forests and mining lands. In exploration and exploitation, the state justifies itself by referring to article 33 of the 1945 Constitution and certain articles in the 1960 Constitution. Various cases in Kalimantan, Papua, Sumatra, or Sulawesi are examples of how the state seeks income through the creation of fast and cheap production, namely direct exploitation of natural resources. A very obvious example is the case of the Amungme-Papua tribal customary land taken by PT Freeport to exploit gold and copper mines. Also the case of the East Bentian Dayak tribal land taken by PT Kahold Utama to be used as an industrial plantation forest (Kusuma, 2014).
- 2) To provide cheap food and cheap labor, the state intervened systematically in the agricultural sector. The exploitation and marginalization of the villagers became its excesses. Rice self-sufficiency programs have led to a swell in the number of landless farmers. We can see on the north coast of Java Island where one person controls more than 50 hectares of land while almost a half of the surrounding farmers are landless. The state not only vulgarly liberated land but forced farmers to plant certain commodities such as sugarcane in the TRI program. The green revolution also became a machine that systematically drove the peasantry out of the village (Elza, 2012).

- 3) To build production support infrastructure and other means, the ruler built various supporting facilities such as roads, housing, offices, factories, and sports complexes or golf courses. Clashes also occurred as in the case of Cimacan, Kedung Ombo, Nipah, or Mrican. For investors, the construction of these various facilities itself is part of the convenience and sense of security and comfort.
- 4) To expand production, state enterprises (BUMN and BUMD) manage and strengthen large-scale plantations. This is done by taking over lands previously controlled by the people. An example is the land of the people of Penunggu (Jaluran), North Sumatra, which is used as a plantation location. The same thing happened in Jenggawah, East Java. Plantations and farmers are also in dispute. As happened in Arso-Papua, Sei Lengan North Sumatra, PIRLOK in Silau Java, Asahan Regency, and Cimerak.

All conquests are carried out by the State in order to impose the implementation of one particular project or program declared as a development program or project. With the concept in the interests of Development, the State seems to have the legitimacy to make all attempts at conquest and oppression of the people. All of the State's actions in conquering and oppressing the people have always been claimed as part of the state's efforts to uphold social, political, and security stability so that the nation-building process can continue. Meanwhile, the efforts of the people to defend their rights are accused of hindering development, and are used as justification by the state and its officials to carry out a number of attempts at conquest or oppression (Y. Setiawan, 2009).

The problem of land acquisition for toll roads that are not complete has resulted in the community blocking the finished and ready-to-use toll roads, so that the investment funds that have been used to make these toll roads are hampered to return the investment such as the JORR Hankam-Cikunir toll road, Kanci Toll Road, Cirebon-West Java, Ulujami Toll Road, and others which consequently harm investors and if not quickly overcome can traumatize investors inside and outside country to invest in the Republic of Indonesia (Hasan, 1996a).

Various land disputes are caused by inconsistent attitudes of implementers of laws and regulations. In practice often the 'public interest' is used as a justification for the taking or, rather, the seizure of people's land by certain large businessmen. Land acquisition chaos in Putat Gede, Tandes District, Surabaya, for example. This case involves community members, Surabaya Municipality Government, and businessmen. The case of land acquisition in Karang Bulak which sacrificed a resident named Mbak Kar is also the case. The land dispute on Jl. Urip Sumoharjo Surabaya also involved residents, municipal governments, and investors (Hasan, 1996b).

In the name of public interest or development interest, land is liberated. It turned out that the land was then controlled by the expanding private sector. For example, the case of land in Tamalanrea, Makassar. This land has been controlled by residents since their ancestors. One time a big fire broke out there. A few days later, the Makassar Municipality Government prohibited residents from returning to their land. Some residents did not evict. The tents and makeshift buildings they erected were bulldozed by the City Government. Material and psychic losses were suffered by the residents

(A.P.Parlindungan, 1999). Obviously, the evictions carried out by government authorities in Surabaya and Makassar are not in the public interest. It is the investors who benefit because they can get cheap land in the name of public interest or development (Ariyanti, 2006).

Another land case occurred because government authorities displaced residents on the grounds that they would build toll roads. The compensation they gave but the value was inadequate. As a result, residents sued to the court (Arisaputra, 2015).

3. Model of Dispute Resolution or Land Clearing of Public Facilities

Good rulemaking without being accompanied by law enforcement can consequently lead to land occupation, encroachment, forgery, or fraud of evidence of land rights. Land disputes should be detected and resolved as early as possible (Sumardjono, 1997). The reality is different. As with disputes in other areas, land disputes can be resolved in three ways, namely:

- 1) Settlement by deliberation.
- 2) Settlement through judicial bodies. Here the issue is filed in the general court in a civil or criminal manner if the dispute is related to the illegal use of land as stipulated in Law No. 51 Prp 1960 on the Prohibition of the Use of Land Without a Rightful Permit or Power of Attorney, or through the State Administrative Court.
- 3) Settlement through arbitration and alternative dispute resolution, as referred to in Law No. 30 of 1999 on Arbitration and Alternative Dispute Resolution. This is an out-of-court dispute resolution effort. Arbitration settlement of land disputes is informal, closed, inexpensive, and more efficient so that it is expected to better meet the wishes of the parties to the dispute. Meanwhile, alternative dispute resolution is an effort to resolve disputes outside the court by means of consultation, negotiation, mediation, consolidation, or expert judgment.

Settlement of disputes in the housing sector based on Articles 147 and 148 paragraphs (1) of Law No. 1 of 2011 should first be pursued based on deliberations for consensus. If the resolution of the dispute through deliberation for consensus is not reached, then the aggrieved party can sue through a court that is in the general court environment or outside the court. Based on the voluntary choice of the parties to the dispute through alternative dispute resolution, this way of deliberation will usually be pursued first by the parties to the conflict before the parties pursue the means of conflict resolution through conciliation, mediation and arbitration and justice. Thus, before resolving disputes through conciliation, mediation, and arbitration and justice, it should be resolved through deliberation first (Sahono, 2012).

The existence of a mediation process carried out in the Court which aims to seek peace in accordance with Article 2 paragraph (4) of Perma No. 1 of 2008 concerning Mediation Procedures in Courts is determined. The judge in considering the judgment must mention that the case in question has been sought for peace through mediation by naming the

mediator. The consideration part of this award will first be considered about mediation between the parties (Santoso, 2005).

Land acquisition for development is carried out by deliberation in accordance with Article 8 of the Presidential Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia No. 36 of 2005 concerning Land Acquisition for the Implementation of Development for the Public Interest. The contents of this article are: 1) The acquisition of land for the implementation of development for the public interest is carried out through deliberation in order to obtain an agreement regarding: a. Implementation of construction in the public interest of the site. b. The form and magnitude of the indemnity. 2) Deliberations are conducted at the place specified in the invitation letter (Setiawan, 2019).

Article 9 of the Presidential Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia No. 36 of 2005 states: (1) Deliberations are carried out directly between rights holders or land, buildings, plants, and other objects related to land with the land acquisition committee, and government agencies or local governments that require land. (2) In the event that the number of land rights holders does not allow for effective deliberation to be held, the deliberations referred to in paragraph (1) shall be carried out by the land acquisition committee and government agencies or local governments requiring land with representatives appointed among and by the land rights holders, who at the same time act as their attorneys. (3) The appointment of representatives or powers of attorney of the rights holders as referred to in paragraph (2) shall be made in writing, with sufficient stamps known to the village head/village head or a letter of appointment/power of attorney made before the authorized official. 4. The deliberations as referred to in paragraphs (1) and (2) shall be presided over by the chairman of the land acquisition committee (Maria, 2008).

Article 10 of the Presidential Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia No. 36 of 2005 states: (1) In the event that development activities for the public interest cannot be transferred or technically transferred to another place or location, deliberations are carried out within a maximum period of 90 calendar days from the date of the first invitation. (2) If after deliberation as referred to in paragraph (1) no agreement is reached, the land acquisition committee shall determine the form and amount of compensation as referred to in Article 13 and entrust monetary damages to the District Court whose jurisdiction includes the location of the land concerned. (3) If there is a dispute over ownership after the determination of compensation as referred to in paragraph (2), the committee shall entrust the compensation money to the district court whose jurisdiction includes the location of the land concerned (Parlindungan, 1989).

Article 11 of the Presidential Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia No. 36 of 2005 states:

"If an agreement has been reached between the land rights holders and government agencies and/or local governments that require land, the land acquisition committee issues a decision on the form and amount of compensation in accordance with the agreement."

In compensation, the problem is related to the economic problems of individuals and society in general. A person who gets compensation will basically still feel a loss because they know that the land they control is of high economic value. Sometimes it is not taken into account so that the person concerned does not want to let go of the land. Referring to Presidential Decree No. 55 of 1993 which relies on real prices that do not match the public who do not want to sell at market prices (Soerodjo, 2003)

C. METHOD

Research in this dissertation belongs to the doctrinal type of research, where the approach method used is normative juridical (Qamar et al., 2017). The normative juridical approach is to understand the problem using the approach of legal regulations or applicable laws and regulations (Ali, 2021). The normative legal research method also called positive law science referred to here is a law that applies at a certain time and place, namely a written rule and norm that is officially formed and promulgated by the ruler, in addition to written laws that effectively regulate the behavior of members of society (Rahayu et al., 2020). This is because the data taken is sourced from cases of land grabbing of public facilities in Indonesia (Susanti, 2015)

D. DISCUSSION

1. Solving the Problem of Criminal Law Land Clearing

Criminal proceedings that can only punish the perpetrators of land grabbers do not provide a single legal certainty for landowners, allowing the raiders to continue to seize the land being raided. It is very dilemmatic of course, but if in the future there is a change and or affirmation in the criminal law rules for the perpetrator of the raid, then the act of breaking the ground can be avoided. This is because ownership of the land that is seized must wait for a court decision with permanent legal force. Similarly, landowners are also advised to exercise control over the land owned, such as fencing the land and cultivating it as planned. This is contained in the intention that if there are people or parties who are not owners, they will give up their intention to enter and or invade the land (Putra, Sukadana, & Suryani, 2019).

The resolution of the issue of land grabbing in criminal law, is still not effective, because criminal proceedings are only punishing the body for the perpetrator of the seizure of land that does not belong to him and the judgment of the court in a criminal case cannot execute the invader to get out of the land he seized. Even though it is criminally proven that a person has committed a seizure of land, has not guaranteed his ownership, and must also file a civil legal process through a lawsuit and after obtaining legal certainty through a civil judgment, then requesting execution to the court, then the ownership of the land that the person seized can be re-owned (Boedi Harsono, 2004).

The most important part of a criminal system is to establish sanctions, the validity of which will provide direction and consideration of what should be sanctioned in a criminal act to enforce the enactment of norms. In a law or regulation, the existence of regulations regarding sanctions or criminal penalties is very important because in criminal law we can

know which acts cannot be done, are prohibited, and must be done accompanied by threats or sanctions in the form of certain criminal penalties for whoever violates these provisions (Bahfein, 2020).

Accounting the defendant for his actions is of no use if the act itself is not unlawful, then it can be said that first there must be certainty about the existence of a criminal act and then all the elements of the error must also be connected with the criminal act committed, so that for the existence of an error that results in the conviction of the defendant then the defendant must: 1. Commit a criminal act; 2. Able to take responsibility; 3. By willfulness or negligence; 4. The absence of forgiving reasons (Kuswahyono et al., 2021).

Criminal sanctions for people who commit these crimes are regulated in Article 385 of the Criminal Code which is one of the articles that are often used by investigators (Police) and public prosecutors (Prosecutors) to indict perpetrators of land grabbing and are categorized as criminal crimes. In particular, Article 385 paragraph (1) of the Criminal Code reads: whoever with the intention of unlawfully benefiting himself or others, sells, exchanges, or burdens with credietverband something rights to land, a building, a building, planting, or hatchery, when it is known that the person who has or has the right to it is another person (Sarkawi, 2014).

The act of land grabbing carried out by a person can be processed and entangled with the articles contained in Law Number 51 PRP of 1960 concerning the Prohibition of Using Land Without Permission and in the Criminal Code, including: Article on land grabbing (if the perpetrator sells land owned by someone else who is legal), Article of Stoning (if there is an element of threat in raiding land, Article of Forgery (If the perpetrator forges existing correspondence), Article of Destruction (if the perpetrator commits the destruction of crops, fences, stakes belonging to the rightful owner), Article of Fraud (if there is an element of deceiving others by deceit and against the law).

In accordance with the provisions of Article 2 of Law Number 51 PRP of 1960 concerning the Prohibition of The Use of Land Without Permission which is still valid today, that a person who uses land without a rightful permit or interferes with the entitled party is threatened with a maximum of 3 (three) months imprisonment. Legal process according to this provision, it is important to have evidence of someone's activities in planting crops, or working on land or erecting buildings/huts on land owned by others. Criminal proceedings use speedy proceedings, where police investigators act as prosecutors in trials presided over by a Single Judge (Afriandari et al., 2021)

The provisions of Article 385 of the Criminal Code (KUHP), that a person who unlawfully, sells, exchanges land that does not belong to him to another party and obtains profits for his actions, is threatened with imprisonment for a maximum of four years. In this case, the element that must be fulfilled is the element of "benefiting oneself or others unlawfully, selling, exchanging", which means the act of a person who sells / exchanges land that does not belong to him to another party and obtains profits for his actions (Yusuf, 2016).

In the process of settlement through criminal channels related to land issues there are several things that must be considered and implemented by the rightful landowner or in other words the victim of land grabbing. This step must be taken by the victim so that later the ultimate goal of this process is to regain the rights that he has but is controlled by others (Setyowati & Asmaniar, 2020).

These steps include: (Reswari, 2014)

- 1) Coordinate/consult with the Police to ensure that the Criminal Act to be reported, either Theft or Occupying Land Without Permission or Land Clearing or Destruction, is the easiest in proving it in accordance with field conditions;
- 2) Prepare and appoint a whistleblower who will report directly to the Local Police (If a Representative is entitled to a Special Power of Attorney);
- 3) Report officially with the creation of a Report (LP) at the Police;
- 4) Receive a report mark in the form of a Letter of Receipt of Report (STPL);
- 5) Seeking a minimum of 2 or more witnesses who are more aware of the conditions of the field and the scene;
- 6) Supervise and follow the Minutes of Examination (BAP) process at the local police, especially legal assistance for whistleblowers and witnesses;
- 7) Prepare evidence (at least 2 pieces of evidence), in the event of:

a) Criminal Vandalism

Documents of land ownership of legal owners, actions of perpetrators (damaging goods / plants / buildings, arable land), the results of actions in the form of damaged goods, photo documentation of activities carried out, photos and tools used.

b) Criminal Theft

Stolen products/stolen residues, tools used, transportation equipment, photo documentation of the scene or slash marks

c) Criminal Occupation of Land Without Permission

Documents of ownership of land that is entitled, documents of land that claim land (if any), activities/activities of actors on land owned by the rightful, photo documentation of activities carried out (land cultivation, planting, setting up huts/buildings), photos of the location of the incident, claim letters and/or other supporting documents.

d) Criminal Land Raids

Land ownership documents of the owner, documents of land claiming (if any), proof of land purchase, photo documentation of activities carried out (land cultivation, planting, building huts/buildings), photos of the location of the incident, claim letters and/or other documents.

- 8) Monitoring of the area to determine the development of land conditions;
- 9) Conduct intensive coordination with the local police to follow up the results of the investigation until it is transferred to the District Attorney's Office (P.21) and processed in the District Court.
- 10) After a court decision with permanent legal force (inkracht), coordination is still carried out to carry out the execution process.

2. Settlement of Land Clearing Issues in Civil Law

Civil disputes over land can occur between individuals or between individuals and legal entities. The disputed are varied, whether it is about the physical data of the land, the juridical data, or the legal acts carried out on the land. Disputes over the physical data of a piece of land, for example, the location, boundaries, or area.

Juridical data disputes lean more towards the legal status (rights to his land), the holder of his rights, or the rights of others that may burden him. Meanwhile, disputes about legal actions can be in the form of actions that create rights, encumbrance of rights with other land rights, or dependent rights in terms of the plot or area of land used as credit guarantees, transfer of rights, extension of the term of rights, renewal of rights, and release of rights (Wahono, 2021).

Land rights disputes can occur due to a lawsuit from a person or legal entity due to legal actions that have harmed the plaintiff's right to land. The material of the lawsuit can be in the form of a claim for legal certainty regarding who is entitled to the land, the status of the land, the evidence on which the rights are granted, and others.

Civil disputes over land can also occur as a result of land transfer agreements, for example by sale and purchase, lease, or inheritance (Dewi, 2018).

The litigation mechanism that is too long civilly, makes the landowner feel that the legal certainty that exists in our country has not guaranteed that the control of his land rights is protected with certainty, on the other hand, the invader can still enjoy the right of control of the land he occupies before a court decision with permanent legal force, then the landowner can apply for execution through the court.

A civil court decision cannot punish the perpetrator because a civil judgment only guarantees ownership of the plaintiff's land (Chomzah, 2004).

The land clearing judicial process, which is too long to be carried out in civil proceedings, is a concern of the parties concerned, especially lawmakers to make additional rules or provisions on the one hand and on the other hand the government in this case the National Land Agency takes the role of socializing to the community who own the land and do not have ownership rights immediately process it, so that the problem of land grabbing can be avoided, as well as the Village / Kelurahan government that owns vacant lands or lands to immediately remind the owners of these lands / lands to be immediately used in accordance with their designation (Dirman, 2018).

Here are the stages that must be passed in a civil case in the trial process: (Hayati et al., 2019)

1) Filing a Lawsuit

The land grabbing suit is filed through the chief justice of the district court which has jurisdiction including the residence or place of residence of the defendant. If the object of the suit is immovable, the HIR does not regulate specifically, but R.Bg gives priority - the suit is filed through the Chief Justice of the District Court whose jurisdiction. Filing of a lawsuit letter regarding land grabbing, namely the owner of the land that is seized by people has strong evidence, among others, Certificates on the land that is seized or Certificates of Property Rights (SHM), Letters about the origin of the land he owns and or chronologically the acquisition of land that is the object of dispute. It is contained in the intention that in the course of the case of the seizure of the land in the evidentiary hearing stage the landowner or plaintiff is able to convince the panel of judges who examined the suit of the landowner and subsequently the trial (Pratiwi et al., 2020).

Similarly, the person who carries out the seizure of land that does not belong to him, is obliged to explain what is the reason or what is underlying the invader's entry, to seize the land in question. These matters are very important to explain in the trial for the importance that the panel of judges who process land grabbing cases will provide legal considerations in the decision of the case later (Husodo et al., 2017).

2) Summoning Stage

Upon filing of a suit for land grabbing which is an act of registration process which includes registration of payment of the panjar of the case and the determination of the panel of judges with the substitute Registrar, subsequently the Chief Justice or his Deputy, and or by the Panel of Judges who shall examine the suit immediately fixed the day of the hearing followed by an order to the clerk or bailiff to summon both parties (plaintiff and defendant) , in order to appear before the court hearing at the appointed time for it. The definition of a summons in civil procedural law is to convey formally and appropriately to the parties involved in a case in court, in order to fulfill and do the things ordered by the Panel of Judges (Saranaung, 2017).

The authority to make a summons is a bailiff by order of a panel of judges based on Ps.12 subsection (1) of the HIR, only the summons made by the bailiff officially from the appropriate is valid and official. Call letters are also called relaas. In the Code of Civil Procedure, these relaas are categorized as authentic deeds. In Ps.165 HIR and Ps. 285 R.Bg and Ps. 1868 B.W., it is stated that an authentic deed is a deed made before a public servant in the form prescribed by applicable law. Likewise with call relaas. Thus what is contained in the relaas must be considered true, unless it can be proved otherwise (Ismi, 2012).

The issue of summons and notification of judgment is contained in articles 122, 388 and 390 of the HIR and Article 146, Article 798 of R.Bg as well as articles 26-28 of Government Regulation No.9 of 1975 and Articles 138-140 of the Compilation of Islamic Law. In the provisions of this Rule it is stated that the technicalities of the summons of the litigants

are as follows: 1. Summons within the jurisdiction 2. Calls outside the jurisdiction 3. Overseas invocation 4. Summons for occult/unknown defendants (Ahyar, 2018)

3) Trial Preparation

The trial that begins before the trial until the completion of the trial is carried out by an officer specially appointed to perform these duties, such as preparing the court equipment, writing the trial schedule on the notice board that has been provided in accordance with the order of registration of the case, calling the parties and witnesses to enter the siding room and so on. Meanwhile, when the trial takes place, it is carried out by the Panel of Judges themselves (Rosdiana, 2020).

In preparation for the trial The minutes of the trial or referred to as the verbal process is something that must be prepared. This siding minutes is an authentic deed made officially by an authorized official containing the process of examining a case in a trial, as the basis for the Panel of Judges in making a decision on the case it is trying (Rajagukguk et al., 2021).

4) Lawsuit Reading

Reading of the Suit At this stage the Panel of Judges will ask the plaintiff whether there is a change in the suit or not, and if there is no change then the Chief Justice shall ask to read out the letter of the suit filed by the Plaintiff, After the reading of the suit letter is implemented, the Panel of Judges will ask the Defendant whether the suit letter read out is understood or not. And if the defendant does not understand, then the Panel of Judges will explain which points are not yet known/understood. If the defendant is familiar with the content of the plaintiff's suit, then the Panel of Judges asks the defendant whether he will answer orally or in writing. Whether to answer immediately or ask the panel of judges for time to draft a written answer first. And starting from that ssat also the process of checking into the answering stage (Samir, 2021).

5) Defendant's Answer

Defendant's Answer This stage is the stage at which the defendant gives a rebuttal or acknowledgment of the arguments of the suit filed by the plaintiff. Therefore, the answer should be prepared based on the arguments of the Plaintiff's suit for easy understanding. The answer is done by first repeating the argument of the lawsuit to be answered first and then giving the argument of the answer. The defendant's answer actually revolves around two kinds: (1) an indirect answer to the subject matter of the case called a case or exception, (2) an indirect answer to the subject matter (Krisdayanthi, 2020).

Proof is an action carried out by the parties to a civil dispute. This proof aims to establish a law between the two parties that concerns a right so that a truth that has the value of justice is obtained. About that truth in the civil proceedings sought by the judge is the truth, i.e. the judge is prohibited from exceeding the limits put forward by the litigants. The provisions of article 178 paragraph (3) of HIR/Article 189 paragraph (3) of RBG/Article 50 Paragraph (3) of RV, expressly prohibit judges from passing judgments on cases that are not prosecuted or pass more than demanded (Fitrianingsih, 2017)

3. Legal Protection against Land Acquisition of Fair Indonesian Public Facilities

Land issues do not only touch on a person's civil aspect, or are also not only limited to the study of state administration which is neatly wrapped in a mere administrative decision, but also relates to the authority of public law (criminal) in it with a certain context that is in direct contact with land rights. Therefore, discussions related to crimes against land are important to be reviewed comprehensively in order to get a complete and comprehensive explanation of crimes that are in direct or indirect contact with land rights (Diab et al., 2018).

The legal phenomenon that arises behind the occurrence of disputes, conflicts and land cases in the midst of society is a result of a situation / situation and conditions regarding rights and obligations and prohibitions that occur not as appropriate apply to a land right held / owned by a legal subject (subject of rights). That is, there is an act that is then considered unlawful and/or a crime against various land rights as regulated by the UUPA and results in the emergence of disputes, conflicts and land cases (Artana et al., 2021).

Therefore, a new concept is needed for the settlement of land grabbing of public facilities and land disputes in general in the future, with the concept of Special Land Courts in the Indonesian Judicial System (Mawati, 2021)

Based on the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia, Indonesia is a country based on law (*Rechtstaat*), not based on mere power (*Machtsstaat*). Government is based on a constitutional system (basic law), not absolutism (unlimited power). In line with these provisions, one of the important principles of the state of law is the guarantee of the free administration of judicial power, free from the influence of other powers to administer the judiciary in order to enforce law and justice (Amelia, 2015)

Judicial power according to the amended 1945 Constitution is an independent power exercised by the Supreme Court of the Republic of Indonesia and the judicial bodies under it, and by a Constitutional Court to organize a judiciary to uphold law and justice. The Supreme Court is the highest state court of the four courts, namely the general judiciary, religious courts, military courts and state administrative courts. In accordance with Article 33 of Law No. 4 of 2004 states that in carrying out their duties and functions, judges are obliged to maintain judicial independence. The power of an independent judiciary that takes the form of freedom of judges in deciding cases is not without risks (Mawati, 2021).

In the United States, this mechanism is pursued through "impeachment" which is a trial *by Congress*. This institution of impeachment implies that taking action against judges is not easy. On the one hand there is a desire to protect the freedom of the judge, but on the other hand there is also a desire to prevent the judge from despicable deeds. It should be emphasized that actions against judges such as the "impeachment" process are not related to the performance of their judicial functions. There is no power that can crack down on judges because their rulings are considered unfair. Actions against judges can only be applied based on personal behavior that is detrimental to the state or degrades the dignity of judicial power (Azhar, 2019).

It has been stated above that the possibility of abuse of the freedom of judges may also occur because the authority attached to extra-judicial powers causes the freedom of judges to be reduced or completely meaningless. In the future these disruptions or attempts to weaken the principle of institutional judicial independence will surely continue. The signs are still present in the various formulations of the aforementioned laws. Now it is up to the leaders and the Indonesian people themselves so that with their intelligence they are still willing to uphold the principle of judicial independence which is institutional and very useful both for the continuity of the state and useful for the protection of the human rights of each individual and leader (Mulyana, 2018).

Everyone, including leaders, when forced to face judicial power or faced with a court hearing will require the protection of human rights guaranteed by the principle of judicial independence in an institutional manner. With the indiscriminate execution of the judiciary everyone will feel bound by the decisions of a fair judge. It can only be achieved by maintaining institutional judicial independence. In addition to judicial independence which is institutional, namely the independence of an institution against the interference of other institutions, judicial independence is also individual, that is, the individual independence of judges in examining, considering and deciding cases submitted to them (Rofiah, 2020).

In Article 24 paragraph (3) of the 1945 Constitution it is stated that "Other bodies whose functions relate to judicial power are regulated in the Act." This article regulates the existence of judicial bodies of a special nature. The establishment of a special judicial body must consider the principles of benefits, efficiency, productivity and an integrated judicial system. This avoids the existence of special courts that sharpen "jurisdictional disputes" due to various overlaps that confuse justitia due to legal uncertainty. Through a special court that handles land disputes, it is hoped that the overlapping authority of the judicial body will not occur again (Mulyani, A., Kuncoro, D., Nursyamsi, D. dan Agus, 2016).

The establishment of such a special judicial body must be regulated in the Law in accordance with Article 15 of Law No. 4 of 2004. In this case, in addition to being able to establish a special judiciary, there are also constitutional examples of bodies or institutions related to judicial power, such as prosecutors, advocates, police, etc.⁵⁴⁴ Article 15 paragraph (1) of Law No. 4 of 2004 states: A special court can only be established in one of the judicial environments as referred to in article 10 regulated by the Law. The definition of "special" in Article 15 paragraph (1) of Law No. 4 of 2004 is different from the special understanding in Law No. 14 of 1970, in this case it gives the meaning of "special court" as a specificity in each judicial environment. Meanwhile, the specificity in Article 15 paragraph (1) of Law No. 4 of 2004 which is intended to mean room (*Raadkamer*).

As we know that in the general judicial environment, there are special courts for juvenile criminal cases, corruption criminal cases, human rights cases. So the intention of the special court in Article 15 paragraph (1) of Law No. 4 of 2004 is specificity (differentiation / specialization). It is also asserted that a special court can only be established in one judicial environment, and a special court is part (chamber) of a judicial environment. For

example, juvenile justice, corruption courts, human rights courts, are within the general judicial environment.

Based on the provisions of Article 15 paragraph (1) jo Article 10 of Law No. 4 of 2004, a special court for settlement of land disputes must be included in one of the judicial environments under the Supreme Court of the Republic of Indonesia, namely the general judicial environment or the special judicial environment of state administration. To determine this, it is necessary to look at the law and characteristics of the land itself and what issues can be heard in the special court of settlement of land disputes.

Based on Article 33 paragraph 3 of the 1945 Constitution and Articles 2 & 3 of the UUPA, we can conclude that land is public law but land has private characteristics. Land disputes are not limited to disputes over the issuance of decrees of State Administrative officials only relating to land, but concern land ownership, land compensation, land acquisition, forgery of land papers, and others. Based on the complexity of land disputes, special land courts need to examine land ownership disputes, the validity of land documents and lawsuits over BPN decisions.

So according to the author, the special court for the settlement of land disputes is more likely to be included in the general judicial environment under the Supreme Court of the Republic of Indonesia. If it is included in the environment of the state administrative court, then it is impossible to change the basis of the lawsuit that has been established in Law No. 5 of 1986 concerning who is being sued and the object of the dispute. This special land court referred to the research of Elza Syarief

The land law regulated by UUPA differs in principles and philosophy from the land law regulated by Book II of the Civil Code, where UUPA is a law that regulates the rights of control over land or the surface of the earth according to Article 4 of the UUPA. The land referred to in the UUPA is not the same as the land referred to in Book II of the Civil Code as immovable objects, but the land in the UUPA has very specific principles and is the cultural culture of the Indonesian nation. Indonesian soil does not fully have the property of a material property as an immovable object based on the Civil Code.

It is therefore appropriate for a special court for the settlement of land disputes to be included in the general judicial environment. With the existence of a special court for the settlement of land disputes in the general judicial environment, anyone who can be sued is not limited, it can be a fellow person or legal entity or with a state administrative official. Similarly, such special land courts may also hear the validity of documents on land, on land encroachment, etc., provided that the object is "land".

Based on these considerations, the position of the special court for settlement of land disputes is in accordance with the arrangements by the 1945 Constitution and Law No. 4 of 2004, and its position is in the general judicial environment under the Supreme Court of the Republic of Indonesia, namely in accordance with Law No. 2 of 1986 concerning the general judiciary jo Law No. 8 of 2004 concerning Amendments to the Law on General Justice jo Article 15 of Law No. 4 of 2004 concerning Judicial Power jo Law No. 14 The year 1970 culminated in the Supreme Court.

The judge has the authority to issue *conseratory beslag* or revicandatoir confiscation of land, as well as regarding orders for postponement of construction of land, emptying of land, to keep the land from changing status during the trial process. The determination was escorted by local security forces. Seekers of justice can go directly to the special court of land to fight for the rights to their land, in the special court of land will be prepared several clerks who are in charge only to provide assistance or provide explanations and help make a lawsuit and prepare evidence / documents about land ownership, in addition to which advocates who have permission to convene in special courts help the parties to the dispute in special courts soil.

Each special court of land has a list of names of special land officers (*Commissioners*) clerks who specifically serve the party who filed the suit and a list of names of advocates who already have a license to speak in the special court of land, in which case the party who will be in the special court of land is free to choose, whether to come forward on their own or be assisted by their attorney, in addition to the names of judges and clerks. Proof in a special court of land is to seek material truth, not formal, then the judge holds an active and completely free role, meaning that there is no provision binding on the judge, and the judge has the authority to determine for himself what must be proved and to whom the division of the burden of proof must be proved by the judge himself.

Because before it is determined that the case is worth hearing, the judge has carefully examined the truth of the lawsuit and the evidence supporting the arguments of the lawsuit and the testimony of the defendants along with the evidence, and it turns out that for example about the seizure and the land that is seized to be built a building and the presence of an agency official who will dismantle a person's building, the judge can issue an order to begin the implementation in order before conducting a trial in place/location. If it turns out that at the hearing the location is found that no delay determination is required, then an injunction may be issued to revoke the original injunction, against which the party may appeal separately to the high court and the judgment of the high court is final.

The special land court has strong coordination with the police, the National Land Agency, the Village Head, the Sub-District Head, the Mayor, the Regent to be able to confirm land data and coordination in the eradication of false letters on land. At this time the National Land Agency is cooperating with the police to carry out the removal of fake land papers circulating in the public. Special land courts may also resolve overlapping Decrees from the departments of forestry, plantations, mining relating to land. In accordance with Article 33 paragraph 3 of the 1945 Constitution.

The special court of land is referred to in the general judicial environment. This court has the authority to examine, handle, adjudicate, and decide all disputes relating to land, both civil and criminal. This court has its own procedural law with material evidence to defend the material law of the UUPA and other land regulations. This court also has its own specifics, namely in addition to judges, clerks, bailiffs, and secretaries, there are also commissioners, appraisers, and BPN officers who will provide land data to judges at any time.

The authority of the judge himself is quite large, namely that he can hold hearings on site; summons the parties related to the dispute, and officials from the competent authorities. If there is no exception that there is a lack of parties or a rebuttal to the judgment, then this special land court will be able to produce a strong judgment. The judgment can only once be taken to the special High Court for appeal. If there is new evidence (*novum*) the review can be submitted to the Supreme Court of the Republic of Indonesia. With the existence of a special land court, it is hoped that land disputes can be resolved and can be executed so that legal certainty and justice are achieved.

E. CONCLUSION

The resolution of the issue of land grabbing is in criminal law as follows: (1) a *report or complaint*, in which the complainant reports a person who is deemed to have committed a crime. (2) *Transfer of the case to the public prosecutor*; For cases that are considered complete in evidence, this is not a problem when the case will be transferred to the prosecutor's office. (3) *Pre-Prosecution*, in judicial practice when the public prosecutor receives the case file devolved by the investigating party, the public prosecutor must examine or review whether the file is complete or not. (4) *Indictment*, is an important basis of criminal procedural law because based on what is contained in the indictment, the judge will examine and decide. (5) *litigation*, which includes the reading of the indictment, the expulsion, the examination of evidence, the prosecution, the Replik Nader requisitor, the duplication of the pleidooi, and finally the judge's ruling.

Settlement of Land Custody Cases through civil procedural law as follows: (1) filing of a *lawsuit*, A land grabbing suit is filed through the chief justice of a district court that has jurisdiction including the place of residence or residence of the defendant, (2) the *stage of summons*, i.e. formally and appropriately conveying to the parties involved in a case in court, (3) *Preparation for trial*; the trial which begins before the trial until the completion of the trial is carried out by an officer While at the time of the hearing is carried out by the Panel of Judges themselves. (4) Reading of the Suit, at this stage the Panel of Judges will ask the plaintiff whether there is a change in the suit or not, (5) The *Defendant's Answer*, this stage is the stage at which the defendant gives a rebuttal or acknowledgment of the arguments of the suit filed by the plaintiff. The defendant's answer actually revolves around two kinds: (1) an indirect answer to the subject matter of the case called a case or exception, (2) an indirect answer to the subject matter. On the *dasr* was carried out evidence which then ended with the judge's ruling.

Legal protection against land encroachment of public facilities in Indonesia that is equitable with the concept of a Special Land Court in the Indonesian Judicial System. The special court of land is referred to in the general judicial environment. This court has the authority to examine, handle, adjudicate, and decide all disputes relating to land, both civil and criminal. This court has its own procedural law with material evidence to defend the material law of the UUPA and other land regulations. This court also has its own specifics, namely in addition to judges, clerks, bailiffs, and secretaries, there are also commissioners, appraisers, and BPN officers who will provide land data to judges at any time.

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